

Cancer Distribution Patterns over 5-Year Period (2016-2020) in Ekiti State Cancer Registry, Ido-Ekiti, Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

Cancer is one of the major disease burdens worldwide and the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular disease. In Nigeria, the survival rate is low due to the high cost of treatment and late presentation at the hospitals. According to the 2020 World Cancer Report, prevention is the “only consideration that will credibly decrease [cancer] burden”. The socio-demographic data of 707 cancer patients spanning over five years (2016-2020) were collected from the Ekiti State Cancer Registry at the Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti (FETHI). Cancer types were distributed as follows in Ekiti state: reproductive (37.2%), breast (33.5%), gastrointestinal tract, GIT, (7.1%), blood and bone marrow (3.1%), colon (3.1%), connective tissue (2.8%), skin (2.7%), metastatic (2.5%), liver and gall bladder (2.3%), brain (1.8%), endocrine (1.8%), kidney (1.6%), lungs (1.0%), lymphoma (0.8%), eye (0.7%) and jaw (0.4%). The number of male and female subjects was 264 (37.3%) and 443 (62.7%), respectively, with 53% of the female subjects presenting with breast cancer. The prevalence of cancer ranged from 0.64 per 100,000 at Ise/Orun LGA to 15.59 per 100,000 at Ido-Osi LGA. The study found that in Ekiti State, cancer occurrence is higher in females than males, the most frequent being cancer of reproductive sites. Furthermore, the average age of cancer patients was 57.8 years.

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Keywords: cancer prevalence, cancer distribution, cancer registry, medical records, Ekiti State, cancer

1. Introduction

Globally, cancer is known as the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular disease with estimates of 6.7 million deaths in 2008 and is projected to rise to 13.1 million deaths by 2030. Morbidity and mortality from cancer are projected to continue to rise to an estimated 11.4 million deaths by 2030 (WHO, 2007a&b). In 2012, the Global Cancer Statistics (GLOBOCAN) estimated 14.1 million new cases of cancer, 8.2 million cancer deaths, and 32.2 million people living with cancer (based on five years prevalence) worldwide. Of these, 57% (8 million) of new cases, 65% (5.3 million) of cancer deaths, and 48% (15.6 million) of the 5-year cancer prevalence cases were reported to occur in less developed regions. Global Cancer Statistics, GLOBOCAN (2020) reported 19.3 million new cancer cases and almost 10 million deaths worldwide in year 2020. Recently, the trend of the disease is increasingly growing, thereby increasing its global burden. Given this, the global incidence of cancer cases is projected to rise to 24 million people by 2050, from which 70% of the predicted will be diagnosed annually from the lower-income countries.

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Cancer incidence among various countries worldwide has shown significant variation attributed to the difference in socioeconomic development, and lifestyle (Ma and Yu, 2006; Ferlay *et al.*, 2010). Other factors such as the environmental, physical as well as geographical locations of cancer patients may be crucial (Ojo, *et al.*, 2014). Data on cancer incidence and mortality in Nigeria is under-represented because the availability and quality of cancer data are poor (National Cancer Control Plan, 2012).

In a recent study, Wei *et al.*, (2021) reported an updated estimate of GLOBOCAN 2020 cancer burden carried out to investigate the changing profiles of cancer burden in China. A descriptive secondary analysis was carried out using data extracted from the GLOBOCAN 2020 database in the study. The study compared the GLOBOCAN 2018 report with that of 2020; incidence and mortality rates of cancer were reported based on data obtained from the National Cancer Registry Report in China. As a result of the findings, future projections of 49% and 62% increment in the new cases of cancer and mortality respectively were estimated to occur in six continents. The study concluded that China is undergoing a transition with increasing lung, gastrointestinal, and breast cancer burdens and that the cancer mortality rate is higher in China than in other developing countries. In Africa, an epidemiological report of cancer revealed that 667,000 incident cases and 518,000 deaths were recorded in 2008 (Boyle and Levin, 2008).

In Nigeria, the cancer burden is increasing gradually. Based on the World Health Organization report, the National Cancer Control Plan (2012) estimated 102,000 new cases of cancer and about 72,000 associated annual deaths in the country. However, cancer incidence was projected to rise to 90.7 and 100.9 per 100,000 by 2020 for males and females, respectively (Awodele *et al.*, 2011). This is because cancer is a disease burden that is poorly addressed in Nigeria (Uchendu, 2020). Moreover, low cancer awareness, late diagnosis, and lack of affordable curative services have been identified as the cause of cancer fatality in this region of the world (Chalkidou, *et al.*, 2014).

Previous works on cancer incidence in Nigeria have been limited to cancer types and frequencies based on gender (Awodele *et al.*, 2011; Uchendu, 2020; Morounke, 2017). An improvement on these was done by Ojo *et al.*, (2016), where geographical locations of cancer cases were included in the study. However, there is need to study the geographical spread of different cancer types to ascertain the possible influence of geology on cancer prevalence as well as the link between occupation and cancer types. This study therefore seeks to bridge this knowledge gap by associating cancer prevalence in Ekiti State with geographical location as well as occupation types. It is hoped that the data will contribute to effective (possibly, even primary) cancer prevention as well as cancer management in the region.

2. Materials and Methods

Data Collection

Records of cancer cases (707 in total), for five years (2016-2020), were extracted from the Ekiti State Cancer Registry located at the Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti (FETHI), Ekiti-State. Out of the five socio-demographic variables needed in this study, such as cancer type, age, gender, residential location, and occupation of the subjects, only three, namely, cancer type, age, and gender were obtainable at the registry. Lack of information on the environmental and socio-cultural factors of patients at the cancer registries has also been reported by Akinwande *et al.*, (2009). However, the availability of residential locations of patients in cancer registry data is important to enhance geographic connection with cancer disparities (Schootman, *et al.*, 2017)

The Medical Records Department of the same Hospital was therefore contacted for the remaining two variables. However, records were ~~only~~ found for only 272 of the total 707 subjects with ~~only~~ 222 out of those 272 cases coming from Ekiti state, while the rest were from adjoining states. Thus, the unavailability of residential locations and occupations for most of the patients poses a form of limitation to this study. The data extraction at both the Cancer Registry and the Medical Record Department was carried out with the supervision of the respective staff members in charge of the records.

Data Treatment

The records of 707 subjects retrieved from the registry were exhaustively analysed to disrobe the distribution of the various types of cancer among various demographic groupings. Cancer prevalence across the 16 Local Government Areas in Ekiti state was computed for the 222 subjects with residence information indicated. Likewise, the distribution of cancers based on the occupation of the same 222 subjects was investigated. The ARC-GIS software was later used for the geo-spatial distribution of the patients’ geographical locations on the map of Ekiti State.

3. Results and Discussions

Distribution of cancer cases reported at the cancer registry (707 cases) by age and gender

The age distribution for all the 707 subjects is shown in Figure 1. The result shows that the patients within the age range of 61-70 years have the highest number 144 (20.4 %) of cancer cases while the neonates (0-10 years) have the least (2 cases, 0.3%). The mean age of the 707 cancer patients is 57.6 years which is close to the average life expectancy of 55.8 years in Nigeria in 2020. The numbers of male and female subjects were 270 (38.2 %) and 437 (61.8 %) respectively. Cancer incidence increased substantially with age from 30 to 80 years. This age group (30-80 years) accounts for 88 % of all the cancer cases reported in the registry. Between ages 0-10 years, 11-20 years, and 21-30 years, cases of cancer among male subjects have the lowest records of 32%, 44%, and 35%, respectively, relative to female subjects in the same age categories, while the highest cases were recorded for males between age ranges 71-80 years, 81-90 years and > 90 years, with 64%, 83%, and 78%, respectively. On the other hand, cases of cancer among female subjects were predominant between ages 31-40 years, 41-50 years, and 61-70 years with records of 88%, 84%, and 72%, respectively. This shows that females are more susceptible to cancer between ages 31-80 while males are more susceptible to cancer above age 71 and beyond.

Figure 1: Age and gender distribution of cancer patients (707 subjects)

Distribution of cancer cases reported at the cancer registry (707 cases) by gender and cancer types

Figure 2 shows the frequency distribution of the different types of cancers for male and female subjects. The cancer cases were grouped into 16 different types based on sites of occurrence. The result shows that cancer of the reproductive sites

has the highest value (37.2%), followed by breast (33.5%), gastrointestinal tract (G. I. T.) with (7.1%), blood and bone marrow (3.1%), colon (3.1%), connective tissue (2.8%), skin (2.7%), metastatic (2.5%), liver and gall bladder (2.3%), brain (1.8%), endocrine (1.8%), kidney (1.6%), lungs (1.0%), lymphoma (0.8%), eye (0.7%) and jaw (0.4%). Out of the 437 female subjects, 54% were presented with breast cancer. The age at diagnosis ranged from less than one year (2 female neonates presenting with colon cancer) to 100 years (a male with prostate cancer). All the 3 cases of cancer of the jaw were in male subjects, while all 237 cases of cancer of the breast were in female subjects. Also, more cases of cancer of reproductive sites were recorded in females (64.8%) than in male subjects (37.2%).

Cancer type distribution pattern by age and gender for 707 cases

A summary of the demographic profile for each type of cancer is presented in Figures 3a to 3p. The distributions show the type of cancer among three age classifications (viz 0-30 years, 31-80 years, and above 81 years) for both males and females.

Figure 3a-p: Distribution of cancer types in male and female subjects among age categories: 0-30 years, 31 – 80 years, and >81 years.

Blood and Bone Marrow Cancers: Eleven blood and bone marrow cases comprised of 1 case each of blood and bone marrow, and 9 cases of leukaemia. Of the cases recorded, 45.45% were for female and 54.55% were for male subjects. The ages of the female subjects ranged from 24 to 76 years, while those of male subjects ranged from 13 to 81 years. The median ages of diagnoses were 66 years and 38.5 years for female and male subjects, respectively.

Breast Cancers: 237 cases of various types of breast cancers were recorded among the female subjects. The subjects' ages ranged from 21 to 90 years, with the mean age of 52.2 years.

Colon: Twenty-two cases of cancer of the colon were recorded at the registry, of which 59.1% were female subjects. The age distribution for this cancer ranged from 0 to 74 years, while those in male subjects ranged from 35 to 83 years. The median ages of diagnosis in the female and male subjects were 51 years and 75 years respectively. The diagnoses for the youngest subjects were recorded in females (less than a year), while the oldest was recorded in a male subject.

Connective Tissue: There were twenty cases listed in this group. This comprised limb (7), bone (3), thigh (4), neck (2), and one case each of the knee joint, elbow, spinal cord, and Iliac. The cases in male subjects were more than twice the cases in female subjects. The ages of the female subjects ranged from 4 to 89 years with the median age of 52 years, while male subjects ranged from 15 to 60 years with the median age of 64 years. The diagnosis for the youngest subjects in both males and females was a limb, while those for the oldest subjects were knee joint (female) and thigh (male).

Endocrine: The 13 cases listed as Endocrine comprise, 5 cases of Pancreas, 4 cases of Thyroid, 3 cases of Abdomen, and 1 case of Spleen. The cases in female subjects were more than twice that of the male subjects. While the age of the female subjects ranged from 30 to 75 years, the age of the male subjects ranged from 47 to 60 years. The median ages for the female and male subjects were 51 years and 57 years respectively. The diagnoses for the youngest cases were Thyroid (female) and Spleen (male), while those for the oldest cases were Abdomen (female) and endocrine (male). There was no case recorded in subjects below 30 years.

Eye: There were 5 cases of this cancer type at the registry. These are classified as follows: two cases of conjunctiva, and one case each of corneal, retinoblastoma, and orbital mass. Sixty percent of the cases were recorded in female subjects. The ages of the female subjects ranged from 12-61 years, with the median age of 49 years, while those in male subjects ranged from 66-68 years, with the median age of 67 years. There was no case of this cancer type in male subjects below 66 years. The diagnosis for the youngest subjects was retinoblastoma (female) and conjunctiva (male), while those for the oldest subjects were corneal (male) and orbital mass (female).

Gastrointestinal Tract Cancers: Cancers of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) ranked third at the Ekiti State Cancer Registry. A total of 50 cases were recorded as follows: gastric (15), rectal (20), omentum (3), caecum (3), oesophageal (2), anal (3), and 1 each of anorectal, antrum, intestine, and salivary gland. Forty percent of the cases were recorded in females, while 60% were in male subjects. The ages of the female subjects ranged from 32 to 82 years, while those of male subjects ranged from 22 to 98 years. The average age for the diagnosis of GIT was 49 years, and there was no case of this cancer recorded for subjects below 20 years. The diagnoses for the youngest subjects were rectal (female) and oesophageal (male), while those for the oldest subjects were caecum (female) and gastric (male).

Jaw: The 3 cases listed as cancer of the jaw comprised one case each of palatal, parotoid, and lip. There was no case recorded in female subjects. The ages of the male subjects ranged from 10-72 years, with an average age of 65 years. The diagnosis for the youngest was palatal, while the oldest was upper lip.

Kidney: There were 11 cases listed as cancer of the kidney at the registry. These comprised of 6 cases of bladder and 5 cases of the kidney; the Majority (72.7%) of the cases were recorded in female subjects. The ages of the female subjects ranged from 10-69 years with the median age of 54 years, while those in male subjects ranged from 22-73 years with the median age of 25 years. The diagnosis for the youngest subjects in both females and males was kidney, while for the oldest female and male subjects was bladder.

Liver and Gallbladder: The 16 cases in this group comprised, 13 cases reported for liver cancer, 2 cases for hepatocellular carcinoma, and one case in the gall bladder. Thirty-seven percent of the cases were recorded in female subjects. The age ranged from 28 to 89 years in female subjects with the median age of 66 years while those in male subjects ranged from 36 to 79 years with the mean age of 55.5 years. There was no case of this cancer recorded in subjects below 28 years. Two cases of hepatocellular carcinoma were recorded in female and male subjects. The diagnosis for the youngest and oldest subjects in both sexes was liver cancer.

Lung: Seven cases were listed as cancer of the lungs at the cancer registry. Of the cases, 42.9% occurrence was recorded in females. The age ranges in both female and male subjects were 60-78 years and 34-71 years, respectively. The median ages for the female and male subjects were 78 and 74.5 years, respectively.

Lymphoma: Six cases recorded as lymphoma comprised of lymph node with 3 cases, and one case each of axillary, tonsil, and gluteal. The male case is twice that of female subjects (33.3% and 66.7%, respectively). The ages ranged from 37 to 44 years in female subjects while those in males ranged from 25 to 83 years. The median ages for the diagnosis were 40.5 and 66.5 years for females and males, respectively.

Metastatic: The 18 cases listed as metastatic comprised of the following: umbilicus with 6 cases, and two cases each of pleural, intraperitoneal, gluteal, and submandibular; and one case each of supraclavicular, gluteal, peritoneal and retroperitoneal. The female cases doubled those of male subjects. The age ranges in female and male subjects were 12 - 91 years and 7 -78 years, respectively. The median ages of both female and male subjects were 53 and 33.5 years, respectively. The diagnosis for the youngest subjects was neck (female) and pleural (male), while those for the oldest subjects were umbilicus (female) and chest (male).

Cancer of the Reproductive Sites: Reproductive cancer has a total number of 263 cases. These comprised, 158 cases of prostate cancer, 54 cases of cervical, 32 cases of ovarian, 12 cases of endometrial, 2 cases each of uterus and genital tract, and 1 case each for priapism, testicular, and vagina cancer. One hundred and three (103) cases of reproductive cancer were found in female subjects, with the age range of 15 to 91 years. On the other hand, there were 160 cases in male subjects, with an age range of 28-100 years. The median ages for female subjects diagnosed with cervical, ovarian, and endometrial cancer were 62, 51, and 68 years, respectively. The youngest female subject was diagnosed with fibro adenoma.

Skin Cancers: 19 cases were listed as skin cancer. The age of the male and female subjects with skin cancer ranged from 35-80 years with an average age of 55.9 years. While there are 11 cases in the male subjects with the age range 35-80 years, female subjects had 8 cases with the age range 42-80 years. The median ages for both female and male subjects were 59 and 50 years respectively.

Brain Cancer: There were 6 cases listed in this category. Of these cases, 66.7% were recorded in female subjects. The age of the female subjects ranged from 61-66 years with the median age of 61 years, while those in male subjects ranged from 38-61 years with the median age of 66 years. The average age of the subjects was 58.6 years.

The most common cancers were breast and cervical cancers among women and prostate cancer among men. The rate of breast cancer is increasing across the globe and presently, it is the most common female malignancy in Nigeria (Olaogun,

et. al., 2020). In this study, 33.5% of the female subjects had breast cancer with the age range of 21-90 with a mean of

52.2 years which is comparable with earlier findings (Das, Lakshmaiah and Lokanatha, 2015), which showed that 11.3% of the females identified with breast cancer in India were younger than 35 years. The result is also like the finding of Ojo, et. al., (2016) at Ife-Ijesa Cancer Registry for all the categories of cancer for both male and female subjects except eye cancer where the researchers recorded more cases in male subjects who were between 0-10 years. The incidence of breast cancer increases with age and a high mortality rate is associated with breast cancer (McGuire, Brown and Malone, 2015). However, poor outcome in breast cancer treatment relates to late presentation, inadequate diagnostic facilities, and various treatment barriers (Olaogun, et. al., 2020). This study also revealed that the proportion of female patients with cancer is higher compared to male subjects (62.7% versus 37.3%). This is consistent with the findings of several authors (Adebamowo and Ajayi, 2000; Adefuye, 2006; Akinwande, et. al., 2009). They showed that cancer of the cervix is ranked second to breast cancer. Of the 273 cases grouped under cancer of the reproductive site, prostate cancer in male subjects is higher (59.7%) and occurred from age 28 to 100 years in contrast to what is observed in the USA, where mostly males above 65 years were identified to have prostate cancer (Aheto, Utuma, and Dagne 2021).

Figure 3 shows the distribution of cancer types among male and female subjects across different age categories. Out of the 237 females presented with cancer, 95.36% are reported with breast cancers between ages 31 and 80 years. Also, more cases of cancer of the reproductive sites are recorded among male than female subjects as 158 out of 263 were reported. The study agrees with the findings of some researchers in other parts of Nigeria (Ojo, et. al., 2016), which showed that breast cancer is the most common among the age group > 20 years and recorded more cases of cancer of the

reproductive sites for males than female subjects. The data obtained further revealed that across the cancer sites, skin, lung, liver, and gall bladder, GIT, the number of males is higher than that of females. This agrees with the findings of a study conducted in England which observed that men were at higher risk of advanced-stage skin, lung, and rectal cancers (Barclay, et. al., 2021). The higher proportion of female patients with cancer of the bladder observed in this study is not consistent with the findings of (Ojo, et. al., 2016) which showed more male patients with cancer of the bladder than female subjects at the cancer registry at Ile-Ife. There are no cases of cancer of the jaw among female subjects and a few were recorded for males. This is in fair agreement with the findings of the study conducted in Malaysia which showed that jaw cancer is higher among males (62.8%) than in female subjects (Ahmad, et. al., 2021).

Geographical Distribution of Cancer Prevalence in Ekiti State

Of the 707 subjects, only 272 have records of occupation and geographical location. Most of the subjects, not surprisingly, were from Ekiti State with about 81.6% subjects represented. Half of the subjects were residents of the northern part of the state. Of the 272 subjects with occupation and residential information records, 222 (84.2%) were from Ekiti State, according to records obtained from the Medical Health Records department of FEHTI, Ido –Ekiti. The prevalence of cancer (number of cases reported in the medical records divided by 2016 population census data as projected by the National Population Commission) ranged from 0.64 per 100,000 at Ise/Orun LGA to 15.59 per 100,000 at Ido-Osi LGA as shown in Figure 4. The results also show that Ido-Osi LGA indicated in red has the highest value of 15.59 per 100,000 population.

Distribution of Cancer Cases by Types, Gender, and Occupation

The distribution of cancer cases based on the occupation, age, and gender of the patients is shown in Figure 5. The subjects were categorized into the following occupational groupings, namely, artisans, civil servants, farmers, students and graduates, neonates, retirees and dependants, clergy and traditional rulers, professionals, and traders. The artisans' group consists of people engaged in bricklaying, carpentry, driving, and tailoring; the professional group includes engineers and accountants; the civil servants' group includes teachers and others in the civil service. The result shows that most of the patients were traders (37%), while the lowest incidence was recorded among the neonates group (0.74 %). The study revealed that 86.48% of the subjects under the civil servants' group were female. Of the 105 cases recorded among traders, 86.67% were females, of which 45.7% presented with breast cancer. Moreover, 86.49% of the total cancer subjects were also female. This result agrees with the findings of Sari et. al., (2020) who showed that women working in offices and those whose jobs require mainly sitting are at higher risk of developing breast cancer among Japanese women. Among the retirees and dependants, 50% have prostate cancer, 16.67% have cancer of the breast, and 5% of both genders have cancer of the gastrointestinal tract. The least recorded cancer types were for lung and blood.

Figure 4: Cancer Prevalence across the LGAs in Ekiti State

Figure 5: Cancer Distribution in Ekiti State as a function of occupation and gender

4. Conclusion

The study found that cancer occurrence in Ekiti State is more frequent among traders than in other occupations. Gender-based analysis also shows that cancer occurrence is more frequent in females (62.7 %) than in males (37.3 %). The study observed a sharp disparity in cancer prevalence with geographical locations: 15.59 per 100,000 in Ido-Osi compared with 0.64 per 100,000 in Ise/Orun. This disparity could be due to environmental factors, possibly the underlying geology of these areas. The various relationships of cancer with age, location, and occupation highlighted in this study could help bring to the fore, some of the socio-demographic factors and environmental issues affecting human health. The data can also contribute to a deeper understanding of the multiple factors responsible for cancer occurrences in the region. It is hoped that these preliminary analyses will stimulate more research efforts towards investigating possible influences of the physical environment and geographical locations on the aetiology of cancer in Nigeria, like what is observed in developed countries.

References

- Adebamowo, C.A. & Ajayi O.O. (2000). Breast cancer in Nigeria. *West African Journal Medicine* 19,179-194.
- Adefuye, P.O. (2006). Knowledge and practice of cervical cancer screening among female professional health workers in a sub-urban district of Nigeria. *Nigerian Medical Practitioner* 50, 19-22.
- Ahmad P, Arshad AI, Jehangir M, Mahmood R, Shaikh GM, Alam MK, et al., (2021) Association of sociodemographic and clinicopathological risk factors with oral cancers: a 19-year retrospective study. *Pesqui Bras Odontopediatria Clín Integr.* 2021; 21: e0037. <https://doi.org/10.1590/pboci.2021.010>.
- Aheto, J. M., Utuma, O. A., and Dagne, G. A. (2021). Geospatial Analysis, Web-based Mapping and Determinants of Prostate Cancer Incidence in Georgia Counties. Evidence from the 2012-2016 SEER Data. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-021-08254-0>.
- Akinwande, O., Ogundiran, T., Akarolo, S.A, Mamadu, I., Dakum, P., Blattner, W., & Adebamowo, C. (2009). Challenges in Treating Malignancies in HIV in Nigeria. *Current Opinion in Oncology* 21, 455–461.
- Awodele O, Adeyomoye AA, Awodele DF, Fayankinnu VB, Dolapo DC. Cancer distribution pattern in south-western Nigeria. *Tanzan J Health Res.* 2011 Apr;13(2):125-131. doi: 10.4314/thrb.v13i2.55226. PMID: 25566610.
- Barclay, M.E., Abel, G.A., Greenberg, D.C., Rous, B. and Lyratzopoulos, G. (2021). Socio- demographic variation in stage at diagnosis of breast, colon, bladder, colon, endometrial, lung, melanoma, prostate, rectal, renal and ovarian cancer in England and its population impact. *British Journal of Cancer* (2021). 124:1320-1329; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41416-021-01279-z>.
- Boyle, P., & Levin, B., (2008). *World Cancer Report*, Geneva. International Agency for Research on Cancer. ISBN-13: 978-92-832-0423-7
- Chalkidou K, Marquez P, Dhillon PK, et al. (2014) Evidence informed frameworks for cost- effective cancer care and prevention in low, middle, and high-income countries. *Lancet Oncol.* 2014; 15: 119–131.
- Das, U., Lakshmaiah, K. C., and Lokanatha, D. (2015). Breast cancer in women of younger than 35 years: A single center study. *J Mol Biomark Diagn* 6:261, 2015.
- Ferlay J, Shin HR, Bray F, Forman D, Mathers C, Parkin DM. (2010) Estimates of worldwide burden of cancer in 2008: GLOBOCAN 2008. *Int J Cancer.* 2010; 127:2893–2917. [PubMed:21351269].
- Global Cancer Statistics (2020) GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. *CA CANCER J CLIN* 2021; 71 (3):209–249.
- Ma X and Yu H. (206) Cancer Epidemiology Global Burden of Cancer. *Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine.* 79: 85-94.
- McGuire A, Brown, J.A., and Malone, C. (2015). Effects of age on the detection and management of breast cancer. *Cancers (Basel)* 7:908-929, 2015.
- Morounke, S.G., Ayorinde, J.B., Benedict, A.O. et al. (2017). Epidemiology and Incidence of Common Cancers in Nigeria. *J Cancer Biol Res* 5(3): 1105.
- National Cancer Control Plan (2012). National Cancer Control Program for 2018-2022) by National Ministry of Health, Abuja, Nigeria. Retrieved online on 13th July, 2021. <https://www.iccp-portal.org>
- Ojo, J. O., Adeola, M. O., Awe, O. O., Oluwaina, Y. T., and Akinyemi, O. A., Omotoso, P. A., Alatise, O.I., Olasode, B. J. (2014). Analyses and Distribution of Various Types of Cancers Recorded in Ife-Ijesha Cancer Registry in the Five Year Period 2010-2014. *Ife Journal of Science* vol. 18, 4 (2016).
- Olaogun, J. G., Omotayo, J. A., Ige, J. T., Omonisi, A. E., Akute, O. O., Aduayi, O. S. (2020). Socio- demographical Pattern of Presentation and Management Outcome of Breast Cancer in a Semi-urban Tertiary Health Institution. *Pan African Medical Journal.* 2020; 36(363). 10.11604/pamj.202036.363.17866.
- Sari, G. N., Eshak, E. S., Shirai, K., Fujino, Y., Tamakoshi, A., and Iso, H. (2020). Association of Job Category and Occupational Activity with Breast Cancer Incidence in Japanese Female Workers: the JACC study. *BMC Public Health* (2020) 20:1106. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09134-1>.
- Schootman, M., Gomez, S. L., Henry, K., Paskett, E., Ellison, G.L., Oh, A., Taplin, S. H. (2017). Geospatial Approaches to Cancer Control and Population Science. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers Prev.* 2017; 26(4); 472-475. Doi.10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-17-0104.
- Uchendu, O.J. (2020). Cancer Incidence in Nigeria: A Tertiary Hospital Experience. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Care*, 5(1), 27-32. Doi:10.31557/APJCC.2020.5.1.27.
- Wei, C., Hong-Da, C., Yi-Wen, Y., and Wan-Qing, C. (2021). Changing Profiles of Cancer Burden Worldwide and China: a Secondary Analysis of the global cancer Statistics. *Chinese Medical Journal* 2021; 134(7).
- World Health Organisation (2007a). [http:// www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs297/en/ index.html](http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs297/en/index.html).
- WHO (2007b). World Health Organization calls for prevention of cancer through healthy workplaces. <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/news/notes/2007/np19/en/index.html>.